

A CASE STUDY ON THE SYMPTOM RELIEF OF MANYASTHAMB(A CERVICAL SPONDYLOSIS) THROUGH A HERBO-MINERAL FORMULATION CAP.CARE NEURO

Dr. Prashanth A. S.^{1*}, Dr. Jeevitha Tapse²

¹Medical Director and Principal, ²Junior Resident

^{1,2}Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa, Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya and Hospital, Hubli.

***Corresponding Author: Dr. Prashanth A. S.**

Medical Director and Principal, Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa, Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya and Hospital, Hubli.

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ABSTRACT

Manyasthamba, as described in Ayurveda, holds renewed significance in the context of modern lifestyle patterns. Traditionally classified as a Vataja Nanatmaja Vyadhi, The Samprapthi attributed by Acharya Sushruta is Kapha-Avruta Vata, where it denotes stiffness in the Manya pradesha(Nape of the Neck). Manyagraha refers to contraction or spasm, whereas Manyasthamba signifies rigidity or immobility. Historically, it was associated with aging, overexertion, or exposure to cold. In contemporary society, prolonged screen exposure, sedentary habits, poor posture, and psychosomatic stress have emerged as key contributors, leading to cervical stiffness, pain, restricted mobility, and neurological symptoms. Anatomical correlates such as nerve root compression, loss of cervical curvature, intervertebral disc space reduction, and osteophyte formation are consistent with cervical spondylosis, a degenerative condition of rising prevalence. Anubhoota Yoga provides a holistic strategy to address these lifestyle-related musculoskeletal and neurological disorders by enhancing physical flexibility, strengthening immunity, reducing stress, and promoting overall mental and spiritual well-being. This article presents one such Anubhoota Yoga protocol for the management of Manyasthamba and associated neurological conditions. Assessing its effectiveness may offer an evidence-based framework for preventive and therapeutic interventions, bridging traditional Ayurvedic principles with modern lifestyle healthcare strategies. **AIM:** To Study the Effect of Capsule Care Neuro in the Disorder of Manyastambha.

KEYWORDS: Manyastambha, Cap.Care Neuro, KaphaAvruta Vata, Cervical Spondylosis.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary era of modernization and accelerated lifestyle, human beings are increasingly exposed to demanding professional, social, and personal obligations. Such a fast-paced routine, often accompanied by psychological stress, has resulted in considerable alterations in lifestyle and daily habits, ultimately disturbing the equilibrium of the biological system. One of the most significant health concerns arising from these changes is the growing incidence of cervical spondylosis. Prolonged occupational sitting with faulty posture, extended hours of computer and digital device usage, irregular work schedules including night shifts, excessive television viewing, and inadequate rest on poorly designed mattresses or unsuitable pillows are among the major contributory factors. Additionally, the habit of maintaining the cervical region in awkward or unsupported positions imposes continuous strain on the spine, thereby accelerating degenerative changes. Collectively, these lifestyle-related stressors are responsible for the rising prevalence of cervical

spondylosis in the modern population, making it a condition of increasing clinical and public health relevance. The International incidence of cervical spondylosis is 2.5 cases per 1000 population. While in India, incidence is 3.5 cases per 1000 population. It is determined by the age of 70 approximately 100 percent of male, 96 percent of female will have some degree of Cervical spondylosis.^[1] Most frequently occurs in office and computer users.

Cervical Spondylosis is a chronic, degenerative disorder of the cervical spine characterized by progressive changes in the intervertebral discs, vertebral bodies, ligaments, and facet joints.^[2] Although traditionally considered an age-related “wear and tear” phenomenon, its prevalence is increasing among younger individuals due to occupational strain, faulty posture, and sedentary lifestyle associated with modern living. Clinical Features most commonly include persistent neck pain, stiffness, and restricted mobility. Patients may also present with occipital headache, radiating pain to the shoulders or

upper limbs, and sensory disturbances such as tingling or numbness. In advanced stages, compression of nerve roots or the spinal cord may lead to motor weakness, gait imbalance, and other neurological deficits. Diagnosis is based on a combination of clinical assessment and radiological investigations. Plain radiographs typically reveal reduced disc space, osteophyte formation, and degenerative changes, while advanced imaging techniques such as CT and MRI provide greater precision in identifying disc herniation, nerve root impingement, or cervical myelopathy. Management is largely conservative in the early stages, focusing on analgesics, anti-inflammatory medications, physiotherapy, cervical immobilization, and ergonomic corrections. Lifestyle modifications, posture training, and regular exercise play a vital role in long-term control. Surgical intervention, including procedures such as anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF) or laminectomy, is reserved for cases with progressive neurological compromise or refractory pain unresponsive to conservative measures.

Manya means Gala parshwa shira, which is back of neck. Sthamba means Nischalikarana means stiffness, rigidity, immobile. Gayadas, commentator on Sushruta Samhita, considers Manyastambha as individual disease.^[3] Charaka considers it as the prodromal symptom of Apatanaka in Vatavyadhi, while in Trimarmeyya Siddhi Adhyaya explain Manyastambha is because of head injury i.e. Shiro Abhighata.^[4] In Ashtanga Hridaya Nidana Sthana, he mentions Manyastambha as a symptom of Antharayama.^[5] In Ayurveda, many diseases are explained as beginning with Avarana, where the normal activity of Vata is blocked. If this is not treated in time, it slowly leads to Dhatukshaya and finally turns into a Kevala Vataja condition. In Manyastambha, the early stage is mainly Sthamba Pradhana, caused by Kapha blocking Vata. When left untreated, this later results in degeneration, making the disease Shoola-pradhanadue to Kevala Vata involvement. The main Nidana of Manyastambha are Divaswapna, resting or sleeping on uneven or improper surfaces, maintaining wrong postures, and frequent upward gazing.^[6] The main features are Sthambha [stiffness of the neck], Ruk [pain], which makes it difficult for the patient to move the neck freely.^[7]

In western medicine, the treatment of cervical spondylosis mainly depends on painkillers, anti-inflammatory medicines, and steroids. These methods usually give only temporary relief and do not provide a complete or long-lasting solution. On the other hand, Ayurveda focuses on a holistic approach, which includes not just medicines but also changes in lifestyle, daily routine, and diet. Considering this, the present study has been designed to assess the role of Ayurveda Anubhoota Yoga, Cap. Care Neuro in the management of Manyastambha (with special reference to cervical

spondylosis) in providing better relief and improving the overall quality of life.

Anubhoota Yogas, though not always codified in the Brihatrayi, are time-tested formulations developed through clinical experience. In today's era of sedentary lifestyle, stress, irregular diet, and changing habits, lifestyle disorders such as cervical spondylosis, diabetes, hypertension, anxiety, and insomnia are rapidly increasing. Ayurveda views these conditions mainly as outcomes of Vata prakopa and Kapha dushti. Hence Anubhoota Yogas, by combining Vata-Kapha shamaka, Rasayana, Balya, and Ojovardhaka dravyashelp in correcting the Dosha Vaishmya, Dhatu Poshana, calming the mind, and delaying degeneration. Their multi-dimensional action makes them especially relevant for neurological and lifestyle disorders in the modern age, offering a practical bridge between classical principles and contemporary health challenges.

CASE PRESENTATION

A truck driver, aged 37 years male, visited the Outpatient Department of Kayachikitsa of Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya and Hospital, Hubli, with Pradhana Vedana of stiffness and pain in the Cervical region radiating to shoulder. He is Unable to move the neck properly and the Pain radiates to shoulder and both the hand, Unable to hold heavy things using hands, headache occasionally and even difficulty in performing the routine activities and driving in the last 5-6 months.

VEDANA VRUTTANTA

The patient was apparently healthy before 6 months. According

To the patient, he gradually developed occasional stiffness in the back of his neck due to Prolonged driving and sitting, after a few days tingling sensation in his right upper limbs, difficulty in movement of the neck, and mild headache. Gradually the pain started radiating towards the shoulder and hands. He took allopathic Medicine for the same and got some temporary relief in pain and the condition repeats and from last 6 months the condition is affecting his day-to-day activities.

PURVA VYADHI VRUTTANTA

He is K/C/O HTN for the past 5 years and is on medication. No other comorbidities seen.

KULA VRITTANTA: Nothing significant.

ASTHAVIDHA PARIKSHA

Nadi: 72bpm

Mutram : Prakrutha, 4-5 times/day

Mala: Prakrutha, once in a day

Jihwa : Lipta

Shabda: Prakrutha

Sparsha: Anushnasheeta

Drik: Prakrutha

Akrithi: Madhyama

DASHVIDHA PARIKSHA

Prakrithi: Vata Kaphaja
 Vikriti: Vatapradhana Kaphanubandha
 Sara: Medo Sara
 Samhanana : Madhyama
 Pramana: Madhyam
 Satwa : Madhyama
 Sathmya : Madhyama
 Aharashakthi : Madhyama
 Vyayamashakthi : Madhyama
 Vaya: Madhyama

General examination

BP: 120/90mmhg Pulse: 80/min
 Respiratory Rate: 18/min HR: 80/min
 Icterus: Absent Temperature: Afebrile
 Oedema: Absent Cyanosis: Absent

LOCAL EXAMINATION: Tenderness present over the back of the neck.

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

Respiratory system: NAD
 Cardiovascular system: NAD
 Gastrointestinal system: NAD
 Locomotor system:

Range of motion

Flexion - Painful Extension - Painful
 Neck movements – Restricted
 Rotation and lateral bending – Painful and restricted.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

It is a single case study, and the written consent was taken from the patient.

CHIKITSA

The Approach of Ayurveda in the cases of Manyasthamba is to retard the degeneration process and provide strength to the Dhatus, pacifying the Vata dosha which has special importance in the management of any degenerative phenomenon.

The general line of treatment of Manyasthamba is Nasya and Ruksha Sweda. In the initial stages of Manyasthamba there is Vata Avarana by Kapha which later, turns out to be a Kevala Vatavyadhi. So, to relieve the obstructing Kapha dosha Rooksha Sweda is to be done.

Description of Treatment Plan

Amapachana-Ajamodadi Churna 1tsp, tid with lukewarm water, Before food -For the duration of 30 days

SHAMANAUSHADHI

1) CAP.CARE NEURO, 1 TID After food with lukewarm water for the duration of 30 days.

STUDY DRUG

Care Neuro Capsule by **Vedas Pharma** is an Anubhoota Yoga designed for the management of Vatavyadhi and other neurological conditions. In the present era, lifestyle disorders like Cervical Spondylosis, Neuropathies, and Stress-related Neuromuscular ailments are on the rise due to sedentary habits, faulty diet, and mental stress, leading to Vata prakopa with Kapha avarana. By combining classical formulations such as Bṛhat Vatacintamani rasa(25mg), Sameerapannaga Rasa(20mg), Ekangavira Rasa (20mg), Vatagajankusa Rasa (30mg), Vatakulantaka rasa(30mg) and Trayodashanga Guggulu (20mg) Sootashekhara rasa(20mg) etc with total of 27 ingredients in a single capsule, it provides Vata-Kapha shamana, Rasayana, Balya, and Ojovardhaka effects. This integrated approach not only reduces pain, stiffness, and neurological deficits but also strengthens Dhatus and delays degeneration, making it highly relevant in combating modern lifestyle-induced neurological and musculoskeletal disorders. Cap. Care Neuro an Ayurveda Anubhuta Yoga is manufactured and sold virtually worldwide by Vedas Pharma, Vizianagaram Andhra Pradesh.

Table1.0 Ingredients and Mode of Action of Cap.CareNeuro.

Yoga	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Prabhava	Mode of Action
Bṛhat Vatacintamani Ras	-	-	-	-	Rasayan a, Ojovardh aka	Enhances nerve strength, improves cognition, balances Vata-Pitta
Ekangaveera Rasa	-	-	-	-	Vata- Kapha shamaka	Effective in hemiplegia, facial palsy, paralysis
Sameerapannag a Rasa	-	-	-	-	Vata-hara, Medhya	Relieves tremors, stiffness, neuromuscular weakness
Sootasekhara Rasa	-	-	-	-	Pittahara, Hṛdya	Balances Vata-Pitta, useful in stress- induced neurological issues
Vatagajankusa Rasa	-	-	-	-	Vata-Kapha shamaka	Reduces chronic pain, spasms, arthritis, stiffness
Trayodashan ga Guggulu	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu, Rūkṣa	Uṣṇa	Kaṭu	Vedana lsth apaka, Śōthahara	Reduces pain, inflammation, cervical/lumbar spondylosis

B. Table2.0 Single Dravyas (Herbs & Raw Substance)

Drug	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaka	Prabhava	Mode of Action
Dasha moola	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu, Snigdha	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Tridoṣa-hara (esp. Vata- Kapha)	Anti- inflammatory, relieves pain, improves mobility
Bala	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	sheeta	Madhura	Balya	Improves strength, nourishes nerves & muscles
Guduchi	Tikta, Kaṣāya	Laghu, Snigdha	Uṣhṇa	Madhura	Rasayana, Tridoṣha shamaka	Rasayana, and reduces inflammation
Atibala	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	sheeta	Madhura	Balya, Vatahara	Relieves neurological weakness, improves stamina
Balamula	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	sheeta	Madhura	Balya	Useful in Vatavyadhi, neuro-muscular weakness
Devadaru	Tikta, Kaṭu	Laghu, Rukṣa	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Kandughna, Sothahara	Vatahara, anti-inflammatory, relieves stiffness
Duṣparsha (Śyonāka)	Tikta, Kaṣāya	Laghu, Snigdha	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Vata-Kapha hara	Anti-inflammatory, reduces rigidity
Eraṇḍa (Ricinus)	Madhura, Kaṭu	Guru, Snigdha	Uṣhṇa	Madhura	Vatanulomana	Relieves constipation, reduces stiffness & Vāta vitiation
Kapikacchu	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	Uṣhṇa	Madhura	Vṛṣhya, Medhya	Dopamine precursor, improves nerve conduction, Parkinson's
Khursani Oma	Kaṭu	Laghu, Rukṣa	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Dipana, Vata-Kapha hara	Improves digestion, reduces ama & stiffness
Lajjalu (Mimosa pudica)	Kaṣhaya, Tikta	Laghu, Rūkṣa	sheeta	Kaṭu	Vranaropaka, Grahi	Mild sedative, useful in neuralgia & inflammation
Lashuna (Garlic)	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu, Snigdha, Tikṣṇa	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Vatahara, Hṛḍya	Improves circulation, reduces pain, anti-inflammatory
Nirgundi	Tikta, Kaṭu	Laghu, Rukṣa, Tikṣṇa	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Vedana sthapaka, Shothahara	Reduces swelling, cervical pain, improves mobility
Rasna	Tikta	Guru, Snigdha	Uṣhṇa	Madhura	Vatahara	Best in Vatavyadhi, relieves pain and stiffness
Sadapuṣhpa	Tikta, Kaṭu	Laghu, Tikṣṇa	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Vatahara	Anti-spasmodic, useful in neural disorder
Shuddha Shilajatu	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Yogavahi, Rasayana	Adaptogen, enhances nerve & tissue strength
Vacha (Acorus calamus)	Tikta, Kaṭu	Laghu, Tikṣṇa	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Medhya, Vatahara	Improves cognition, reduces nervous disorders
Yavani	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu, Rūkṣa	Uṣhṇa	Kaṭu	Dipana, Vata-Kapha hara	Improves digestion, relieves stiffness, removes ama

RESULTS**Table 3.0.**

SL NO	SYMPTOMS	BT	AT
01	Neck pain	3	1
02	Neck stiffness	3	1
03	Headache	1	0
04	Movements	3	1

RESULTS IN PERCENTAGE**Table 4.0: Depicting the percentage in relief.**

SL NO	SYMPTOMS	PERCENTAGE RELIEF
01	Neck pain	66.6%
02	Neck stiffness	66.6%
03	Headache	100 %
04	Movement	66.6%

DISCUSSION

In the present era, Manyastambha (cervical spondylosis) is increasingly common due to sedentary lifestyle, faulty posture, stress, and lack of physical activity. The Ayurveda emphasizes Doshapratyanika Chikitsa with focus on Vata-Kapha shamana, Sthambha-hara and Ruja-hara therapies. External treatments such as Ruksha Sveda to reduce Kapha Dosha, Greeva Basti with Vatahara Tailato pacify Vata and nourish deeper structures, are highly effective. Internal administration of Rasayana, Vatahara and Medhya formulations like Care Neuro Capsule further supports neuromuscular strength, relieves stiffness, and prevents degeneration. Along with these, lifestyle modifications including ergonomic correction, yoga, and stress management are integral. Thus, Ayurveda offers a comprehensive approach by addressing the root cause, alleviating symptoms, and improving quality of life in Manyastambha.

Capsule Care Neuro is a Herbo-Mineral formulation specifically designed for the management of Neurological disorders such as Manyastambha (cervical spondylosis). The pathology of Manyastambha involves Kapha-avrita Vata, where the obstructive and heavy qualities of Kapha block the normal gati of Vata, resulting in stiffness, pain, and neuromuscular dysfunction. The therapeutic approach therefore requires both Kapha-Vata shamana and nourishment of the Mamsa-Sanyu-Asthi and Majja dhatu. The herbo-mineral components of Care Neuro play a crucial role in addressing this pathology. Brihat Vata Chintamani Rasa acts as a potent Rasayana and Vatahara, enhancing neuronal strength and conductivity. Sameera Pannaga Rasa alleviates Vata disorders with predominant features of tremors, stiffness, and spasm, while Ekangaveer Rasa is traditionally indicated in Pakshaghata and Hanustambha, improving neuromuscular coordination. Sootashekhar Rasa supports Agni deepana and ama pachana, thereby preventing metabolic toxins from obstructing the channels and indirectly pacifying Vata.

The herbal ingredients complement these effects through their Rasayana and Medhya properties. Ashwagandha

provides strength and rejuvenation to Mamsa and Snayu Dhatu, thus reduces inflammation, and aids in nerve regeneration. Brahmi and Shankhapushpi act as Medhya Rasayana, enhancing memory, calming the nervous system, and promoting stress adaptation.

Jatamansi contributes to mental stability, reducing anxiety and promoting sound sleep, which are often disturbed in chronic neurological conditions. Together, these drugs act synergistically to pacify Vata, Kapha shaman and Ama nirharana, relax muscular rigidity, and nourish neural tissues.

Thus, the mode of action of Care Neuro Capsule can be understood as Samprapti Vighatana at multiple levels as it removes srotorodha by reducing Kapha, restores the gati of Vata, does the Poshana of Dhatu through Rasayana karma, and improves mental resilience via Medhya dravyas. Provides a holistic approach by not only addressing the Dosha (Vata-Kapha imbalance), Dhatu (Majja, Mamsa) but Manas (mind) simultaneously i.e the improves mental resilience via Medhya dravyas.

Clinically, this leads to reduction of pain and stiffness, improvement in cervical mobility, enhancement of neuromuscular function, and better quality of life in patients suffering from Manyastambha. Its importance lies not only in symptomatic relief but also in preventing progression and degeneration, making it a valuable integrative intervention in neurological disorders.

CONCLUSION

The administration of Care Neuro Capsule has shown promising results in reducing stiffness, pain, and restricted mobility in Manyastambha, thereby offering a comprehensive and sustainable therapeutic approach with clinical relevance.

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